

CEO Attributes and Financial Performance of Listed Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

Drawing on the CEO attributes and financial performance literature, we use a pooled data design to investigate the effect of CEO nationality and tenure on the financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria over a period of ten years using data collected from 112 listed firms. The data were handpicked from the annual reports and accounts of the sampled firms and analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistical analyses techniques based on a multiple regression model. It is found that financial performance is significantly affected by CEO nationality and tenure. This study provides some evidence to support the Agency theory and the cost and benefit hypothesis. The study is limited by the number of samples, specifically 112 listed firms. It is expected that further research can increase the total sample of companies by adding to the research period or using total population of listed firms in Nigeria. Our study results show that the R-square value is 17 percent, further research is expected to be able to add to this figure. This reflects differences between the financial performance value in Nigeria and stakeholder approaches more common in other climes. Our results could help regulators, and others (e.g., investors) to better understand the potential performance implications of the appointment of directors of different nationality and tenure.

Keywords:

CEO Nationality, CEO Tenure, Financial Performance, Firm Size, Leverage, Profitability, Nigeria, Share Price

JEL Classification Codes:

G2, G32, G34

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1. Introduction

1.1 Financial performance

Financial performance has been severally examined in relation to a wider corporate governance lens (Adekunle & Aghedo, 2014; Aggarwal, 2013; Goel, 2018; Gruszczynski, 2006; Gürbüz et al., 2010; Hakimah et al., 2019; Makki & Lodhi, 2013; Paniagua et al., 2018; Rossi et al., 2015; Shahwan, 2015). In some specific cases, financial performance has been related to board of directors (Abu et al., 2016; Assenga et al., 2018; Di Biase & Onorato, 2021; Ghosh & Ansari, 2018; Hamad et al., 2021; Hsu, 2010; Oyedokun, 2019; Ujunwa, 2012; Uyar et al., 2020; Wahba, 2015) or board committees (Berezinets et al., 2017; Carter et al., 2007; Carter et al., 2010; Edogbanya & Kamardin, 2015; Green & Homroy, 2018; Hoque et al., 2013; Mihail et al., 2021; Puni, 2015; Singhanian et al., 2022).

In other cases, financial performance is examined in relation to ownership structure of corporations (Aymen, 2014; Acero et al., 2017; Haija & Alrabba, 2017; Balagobei & Thirunavukkarasu, 2017; Ben & Boulila, 2014; Cui et al., 2019; Kirimi et al., 2022; Lappalainen & Niskanen, 2012; Lee, 2008). There are handfults scholarly efforts that relate financial performance with the CEO of a firm (Callan & Thomas, 2014; Dalton & Dalton, 2011; Jalbert et al., 2013; Uyar et al., 2021; Weng & Chen, 2017). This is the focus of this article, which is to determine whether financial performance volatility could be made stable and healthy by the power of the CEO?

Keeping up-to-date on the firm's financial performance can help you decide whether the firm is currently able to pay its debt obligations, which might cause you to find sales opportunities. All publicly held corporations are required to send their annual profits on their sites. Mostly, there can be a connection for investors or investor relations on a firm home page that would bring you to business information, including the signal of the firm's annual earnings. It is a great idea to see valuable information about the organisation's strategy and business financial performance.

Given the importance of a sound financial performance in the life of a firm, there is a need to determine which change stakeholder agent that could bring stability to a firm financial performance situation. Several change agent stakeholders have been examined in the past as variously indicated by the gamut of empirical works cited in this paper. In this article, the power of the CEO of a firm to bring financial stability to financial performance fluctuation or low financial performance is the focus of this article.

1.2 CEO Attributes

The CEO of a firm is responsible for making major corporate decisions, managing overall operations, and setting the company's strategic direction. They are accountable to the board of directors or stakeholders of the company and are often the public face of the organization. A CEO one of a number of corporate executives charged with the management of an organization. CEOs find roles in a range of organizations, including public and private corporations, non-profit organizations and even some government organizations (notably state-owned enterprises). The CEO of a corporation or company typically reports to the board of directors and is charged with maximizing the value of the business, which may include maximizing the share price, market share, revenues or another element. In the non-profit and government sector, CEOs typically aim at achieving outcomes related to the organization's mission, usually provided by legislation. CEOs are also frequently assigned the role of main manager of the organization and the highest-ranking officer.

In this article, CEO power is seen in the context of CEO attributes. Of particular interest are CEO nationality and CEO tenure. CEO nationality defines the country of origin of a firm CEO. CEOs' nationality race against time and is especially urgent when it comes to fluctuations in financial performance. Over the last few years, CEOs see poor financial performance primarily impacting their cost profiles and supply chains. Similar, CEO tenure, the time a person spends in the CEO

position, is a key observable characteristic of the CEO that has attracted considerable attention in the fields of management (specifically, accounting and finance). The remaining part of this articles deals with literature review, methodology, results, discussion of findings, conclusion and recommendations.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Agency Theory

Agency theory was developed by Jensen and Meckling (1976) explained that the company's management as an agent for shareholders, acting for their own interests not as a party that sided with the shareholders as assumed in the stewardship model. Agency theory explains that management cannot be trusted to act in the best way for the public interest in general. Thus, managers cannot be trusted to do their jobs - which of course is to maximize shareholder value (Rusdiyanto & Narsa, 2019; Gazali et al., 2020). In these words, the CEO is seen as core part of management. This article is based on the agency conflict arising the clash of interests of CEOs and shareholders. The agents are the CEOs and the shareholders are the principals. Agency theory tries to offer clearance over conflict between the agent and principal.

2.2 Empirical Evidences

2.2.1 CEO Nationality, Tenure and Financial Performance

In 2007, Jalbert et al. examined the interrelationship of CEO Nationality with Financial Management, Firm Performance, and CEO Compensation. The data for the study was derived from the Forbes 800 CEOs. The data extended from 1991-1997 and included 4,834 observations. The study found some evidence to suggest that Central and South America born CEOs, and Australian and New Zealand born CEOs earned a higher return on assets than other CEOs.

Sanda et al. (2010) investigate the effects of certain corporate governance mechanisms on the performance of firms listed on the Nigerian Stock Exchange using a sample of 93 firms for the period 1996 through 1999. Their results showed that expatriate CEOs performed better than their local counterparts.

Sanda et al. (2011) examined the relationship between board independence and firm financial performance. The paper found that foreign chief executives performed better than their local counterparts. In a broad cross-section of US firms, Dikolli et al. (2014) documented that the likelihood of a CEO's performance-related dismissal declines in his tenure.

Badru and Raji (2016) expanded the understanding of corporate governance mechanisms and company performance in Nigeria. The fixed and random effect estimators are employed to identify the variables that influence the performance of public listed companies on the Nigerian Stock Exchange. The empirical analysis shows that CEO nationality statistically influenced company performance.

Ibrahim and Ahmad (2017) investigate certain physical characteristics of the CEO in relation to accounting (ROE) and market-based (market value) firm performance. The paper applied OLS with robust standard errors to a panel composed of 1600 firm-year observations of non-financial Malaysian listed companies between 2010 and 2014. The results revealed that the ethnicity (Chinese) and nationality (foreign) of a CEO have a significant positive association with both proxies of firm performance.

Kaur and Singh (2018) employed a sample of Nifty 500 firms to establish relationship between CEO and firm's financial performance. They considered CEO nationality as CEO characteristic and return on assets (ROA) as a representative for firm performance. The reported findings specify a negative relationship between CEO nationality and firm performance, thus indicating that

nationality acts as a negative inducement for executives to yield finer firm performance.

Elsharkawy et al. (2018) investigate the impact of board diversity and CEO educational background on bank performance using a sample of 54 UK publicly listed banks over the period 2005–2015. Their results denoted a negative and significant impact of nationality diversity on bank performance.

Khan et al. (2021) analyzed the effects of CEO key attributes on the financial performance of 20 banks in Pakistan for 2011 to 2020. The main results revealed that CEO nationality has no significant relationship with the financial performance of the banks.

Rehman et al. (2021) investigated the case of 200 listed Pakistani firms to unravel the kind of nexus that does exist between CEO attributes and firm performance. They employed robust Panel Modeling Methodologies for analyzing data of these sample firms for the period 2010 to 2019. Their empirical estimations highlight that non-national CEO are considered not been the wise choice in Pakistani context. Also, Rehman et al. (2021) also investigated the case of 200 listed Pakistani firms to unravel the kind of nexus that does exist between CEO attributes and firm performance. They employed robust Panel Modeling Methodologies for analyzing data of these sample firms for the period 2010 to 2019. Their empirical estimations showed that CEO tenure is negatively associated with a firm's performance in Pakistan.

Ahmad et al. (2022) investigated the effect of CEO characteristics (CEO tenure, CEO nationality) on firm performance in the context of food and beverage firms in Indonesia, Malaysia and Singapore. The sample was screened from 50 food and beverage firms consisting of 16 Indonesian firms, 19 Malaysian firms and 15 Singapore firms. The period of observation ranged from 2013 to 2018. This study used panel data regression analysis, including the fixed effect model (FEM) with clustered standard errors. The empirical results showed that CEO nationality has a significant effect on firm performance.

Also, Ahmad et al. (2022) investigated the effect of CEO characteristics (CEO tenure, CEO nationality) on firm performance in the context of food and beverage firms in Indonesia, Malaysia and Singapore. The sample was screened from 50 food and beverage firms consisting of 16 Indonesian firms, 19 Malaysian firms and 15 Singapore firms. The period of observation ranged from 2013 to 2018. This study used panel data regression analysis, including the fixed effect model (FEM) with clustered standard errors. The empirical results showed that CEO tenure does not have significant effect on firm performance. Based on these evidences, this article states that:

H₁: CEO nationality has no significant influence on firm financial performance.

H₂: CEO tenure has no significant influence on firm financial performance.

3. Methodology

3.1 Sample

The NGX 156 listed firms constitute the population of the study. Out of this number, 112 companies form the sample for our analysis divided into: agriculture 5, conglomerates 8, construction/real estate 6; consumer goods 17; financial services 31, healthcare 6. ICT 6, industrial goods 11, natural resources 2, oil and gas 5, and services 15. The data for our analysis is sourced from the NGX database created by the Nigerian Exchange Group.

3.2. Empirical Model and Variables

We examine the effect of CEO attributes on financial performance the following model, derived from the existing literature:

$$FP_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 CNAT_{i,t} + \beta_2 CTEN_{i,t} + \beta_3 LEVG_{i,t} + \beta_4 FSIZ_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas:

FP = Financial performance, measured by end of December share price.

3.2.1 Dependent Variable: Financial Performance (FP)

Consistent with the previous literature, we use share price performance as a measure of financial performance. The share price is the average of beginning and end of year share prices. High value of share price indicates high financial performance.

3.2.2 Independent Variable: CEO Attributes

In order to analyze the nationality of a firm CEO, we used a dummy variable, which equals one if a firm has a foreign CEO in a given year of consideration. 0 otherwise. In the case of CEO tenure, we used a dummy where "1" is assigned to companies that have CEOs that have stay for 3 years and "0" for CEOs with less than 3 years tenure.

3.2.3 Control Variables

Although, we are investigating how CEO attributes can influence the extent of firm financial performance, there are other firm level factors that can influence financial performance and which requires to be controlled for in the estimations. On the basis of earlier studies we consider financial leverage (*D/E*) and firm's size (*size*) as the control variables.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1 Summary Statistics

As mentioned in Section 3.1, our sample consists of the 112 firms that trade in the Nigerian Exchange. Summary measures of variables of interest are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
FP	1120	10.094	10.351	.5	47.95
CNAT	1120	.263	.441	0	1
CTEN	1120	.681	.467	0	1
LEVG	1120	.762	.22	.315	2.478
FSIZ	1120	7.653	.509	5.97	9.03

STATA 16 Outputs

Based on the results in Table 1, the number of observations is 1,120 (10 years x 112 firms). Financial performance (FP) averages 10.094 naira per share, while its standard deviation is 10.351, which is higher suggesting that financial performance is volatile and deserves to be researched. The minimum and maximum financial performance value are .5 naira and 47.95 naira, respectively. Similarly, CEO nationality (CNAT) averages .263, with standard deviation of .441. The minimum and maximum CNAT value are 0 and 1, respectively. In the same vein, CTEN averages .681, with a standard deviation of .467. The minimum and maximum CTEN value are 0 and 1, respectively. Furthermore, leverage (LEVG) averages 76.2 percent, with a standard deviation of 22 percent. The minimum and maximum LEVG value are 31.5 percent and 247.8 percent, respectively. Finally, firm size (FSIZ) averages 7.653, with a standard deviation of .509. The minimum and maximum FSIZ value are 5.97 and 9.03, respectively.

Table 2**Results of Diagnostic Tests**

Serial	Test	Value
1	Normality of Residuals	.102
2	Homoscedasticity of Residuals	.124
3	Model Specification Error (ovtest)	.112
4	Multicollinearity (Mean VIF)	1.32
5	Panel Effects	.536

STATA 16 Outputs

The results in Table 2 show absence of normality and homoscedasticity of residuals. Also, there is no evidence in the results to support existence of model specification errors. Furthermore, there is no correlation among the independent and control variables as the mean variance inflation factor is less than 10. In addition, the results of the panel effects test show that there is no panel effects in the data set and therefore, the study pooled the data together and used Ordinary Least Squares Regression (OLS) analysis technique.

4.2 CEO Attributes and Financial Performance

The core research question in this paper is to assess whether CEO attributes lead to better or lower financial performance. Table 3 presents the results of OLS pooled data analysis.

Table 3**Linear regression**

FP	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
CNAT	-5.621	1.815	-3.10	.002	-9.207	-2.036	***
CTEN	3.526	1.686	2.09	.038	.195	6.857	**
LEVG	6.857	3.522	1.95	.053	-.102	13.817	*
FSIZ	-5.033	1.567	-3.21	.002	-8.129	-1.936	***
Constant	42.289	12.7	3.33	.001	17.192	67.386	***
R-squared		0.171	Number of obs		153		
F-test		7.644	Prob > F		0.000		

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

STATA 16 Outputs

Based on the results in Table 3, CEO nationality is significant in relation to financial performance. This is because its p-value is less than the level of tests of significance. Therefore, hypothesis one, which states that CEO nationality has no significant effect on financial performance is hereby rejected and the alternate hypothesis is accepted. In the same vein, CEO tenure is significant in relation to financial performance. Thus, hypothesis two, which states that CEO tenure has no significant effect on financial performance is hereby rejected. The alternate hypothesis is accepted. These results are consistent with a number of empirical studies: CEO nationality (Jalbert et al., 2007; Sanda et al., 2010, 2011; Dikolli et al., 2014; Badu & Raji, 2016; Ibrahim & Ahmad, 2017; Kaur & Singh, 2018; Elsharkawy et al., 2018; Khan et al., 2021; Rehman et al., 2021) and CEO tenure (Ahmad et al., 2022; Rehman et al., 2021).

4.3 Effect of Control Variables

We talk about the effects of the control variables on financial performance in this section. Firms with high gearing, show significantly greater opportunistic financial performance. Firm size shows

negative significant effect on financial performance. All of these results are confirming the previous literature. Furthermore, debt-equity ratio increases firm financial performance as expected on the basis of earlier studies, the result is significant.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the effects of CEO attributes on financial performance of listed firms in Nigeria. In this research paper, the following hypothesis are tested:

H₁: CEO nationality has no significant effect on firm financial performance in Nigeria.

H₂: CEO tenure has no significant influence on firm financial performance in Nigeria.

However, having seen the results in Table 3 in particular, the two hypotheses are hereby rejected and the alternate hypotheses accepted, which state that CEO nationality and tenure have significant effects on firm financial performance in Nigeria. The theory indicates a relationship between CEO characteristics and firm financial performance. The presented research results can be used by regulators, shareholders and boards of directors in ensuring good appointment or engagement of a firm CEO.

Data availability

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Declarations

Conflict of interest

None.

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